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PHYSIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF A CORPUS CALLOSUM

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ANNOTATION

The article is devoted to the problem of influence of the structure of the corpus callosum and the dominant hemisphere on the course of processes of attention and thinking. The basic physiological features and functions of the corpus callosum and physiological bases of attention and thinking are described.

Key words: corpus callosum, attention, thinking, dominant hemisphere, function, adaptation, functional asymmetry.

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ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ МОЗОЛИСТОГО ТЕЛА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена проблеме влияния строения мозолистого тела и доминантного полушария на протекание процессов внимания и мышления. Описаны основные физиологические особенности и функции мозолистого тела и физиологические основы внимания и мышления.

Ключевые слова: мозолистое тело, внимание, мышление, доминантное полушарие, функция, адаптация, функциональная асимметрия.

ISMATOVA Marg'uba Shavkatovna
Samarqand Davlat tibbiyot universiteti

QADOQSIMON TANANING FIZIOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqola qadoqsimon tana va dominant yarim sharning tuzilishining diqqat va fikrlash jarayonlariga ta'siri muammosiga bag'ishlangan. Qadoqsimon tananing asosiy fiziologik xususiyatlari va funktsiyalari va diqqat va fikrlashning fiziologik asoslari tavsiflanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Qadoqsimon tana, diqqat, fikrlash, dominant yarim shar, funktsiya, moslashish, funktsional assimetriya.

Relevance of the topic. In this article the questions of the structure of the corpus callosum (callosum bodies) and its physiological features according to modern ideas are considered. The corpus callosum (CC) is the largest bundle of nerve fibers in the entire nervous system, the most important axonal nerve pathway, 7-9 cm long, connecting similar areas of the left and right cortex.

Work objective. The main purpose of the study is to study the normal physiological features of the corpus callosum, relying on modern representations.

Associative integration between the two hemispheres of the large brain is known to occur through adhesions of white matter, among which the largest and densest is the corpus callosum, which has attracted interest since about the 16th century. For a long time it was considered a «seat of the soul», until in the 18th century Franz Josef Gal and Johann Sprungaim, by dissecting the brain, discovered and described bundles of nerve fibers passing through it and connecting the two hemispheres.

Research methods. It is known that CC ripens up to 20 years, and some data suggest that it lasts up to 25 years. CC is a conduit for both braking and excitation, which can occur at different times or simultaneously in accordance with the task. The CC makes it possible to form an inter-hemisphere organization of psychic processes at a regulatory, mediated, arbitrary level.

CC functions: 1) Transmission of first-processed sensory information; 2) Transfer of lateral verbal or visual-spatial information; 3) Strengthening of interhemispheric interaction while increasing the difficulty of the task performed; 4) Inter-hemispheric braking capability for differentiation of hemispheric activity and more efficient information processing; 5) Ensuring the interaction of those brain structures that are responsible for the mobilization of regulatory resources in the process of human adaptation; 6) Formation of hemispheric dominance of the brain - the smaller some parts of CC, the more functional asymmetry is expressed.

There are differences in mental organization when one hemisphere dominates.

In left hemisphere domination, man can easily operate with words, conventional signs, symbols, inclination to abstraction and generalization, has verbal-logical character of cognitive processes, verbal, theoretical intellect. Left hemisphere is responsible for the account, writing; provides analysis, abstract, conceptual and two-dimensional thinking. The information coming into the left hemisphere is being processed sequentially, linearly, slowly.

The right hemisphere operates on images of real objects, is responsible for orientation in space and perception of spatial relations. Provides synthetic brain activity; visually-shaped thinking associated with a holistic view of the situation and the changes in it that are desirable to get. Information from the right hemisphere is being processed quickly. When dominated by the right hemisphere, man possesses non-verbal, practical intelligence, ability to draw, has musical hearing, artistry, success in sports.

As we see, the CC and the dominant hemisphere must influence the psychic processes of attention and thought.

The physiological basis of attention is the principle of dominance (according to A.A.Ukhtomsky), or the dominant hotbed of arousal. Random attention is provided by selective activation of cortical areas and their functional integration, which are under the control of the frontal cortex.

There is ample empirical evidence of hemispheric contributions to selective attention. According to these data, the right hemisphere is largely one of general human mobilization, maintaining the necessary level of wakefulness and relatively little related to the specifics of specific activities. The left is more responsible for the specialized organization of attention according to the peculiarities of the task. The impact of CC on attention has not been studied.

The process of thinking is a complex analytic-synthetic activity of the cortex of the large hemispheres of the brain, for which complex time bonds (associations) formed between the brain ends of analyzers are important. Refining and embedding these relationships is the basis for more or

less accurate and correct knowledge about the outside world. In addition, the second signal system, i.e. speech, plays a major role in the process of thinking.

Because of the abundance of fibres in the corpus callosum, it was first assumed that this massive structure would have some important function associated with the correlation of activity between the two hemispheres of the large brain. However, when laboratory animals destroyed their corpus callosum, it was initially difficult to detect brain damage. Therefore, for a long time, the function of the corpus callosum was unknown.

Rezult. Since then, numerous studies have shown that its known functions include: inter-hemispheric exchange of information, integration of incoming information reaching one or both hemispheres, promoting certain cortical activities and inhibiting cortical functions. Recently, it has been shown that the size of the corpus callosum in humans is positively correlated with intelligence, and that its integrity is important for cognitive representations.

The lower surface of the corpus callosum is notable in that a few days from the middle of its trunk the body of the cerebral arch (fornix cerebri) is fused with it, which is also a limbic brain and therefore has a characteristic ring-shaped structure. Due to the fact that it consists of nerve fibers connecting the nipple body to the hippocampus, it should be completely attributed to the olfactory brain, that is, to the old cloak formation (archipallium).

Conclusions: According to the literature, about 106 nerve fibers pass through the corpus callosum, which makes an associative connection between the nerve cells of the new cortex of both hemispheres. In the knee of the corpus callosum, there are closed interocular fibers of the frontal lobe, in the trunk there are concentrated fibers of the frontal and parietal lobes, and in thickening (cushion) fibers of the occipital and posterior sections of the temporal lobe converge. According to the existing ideas, the integration of the front sections of the temporal lobes is carried out separately by means of front adhesion. But here we think it is possible to point out that the front of the temporal lobe, the white matter of which contains the amygdala nucleus, belongs to the entorinal region, which is the limbic brain. But at the same time, the corpus callosum, as a single anatomical formation, belongs to the encircling it on the upper surface of the medial and lateral strips, which, according to the literature, carry out associative interactions between distant limbic brain formations.

In addition, the bottom of the corpus callosum is fused with the body of the brain, which is uniquely related to the limbic brain. Apparently, this anatomical and physiological close relationship between the corpus callosum and the cortex points directly to the associative interaction between the new and old placelic brain formations.

It follows from this that the corpus callosum is needed to coordinate the brain and transmit information from one hemisphere to another. And when studying myelo-architectonics of the corpus callosum, it is necessary to take into account the peculiarity of these connections, which has not found its reflection in the literature.

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